

Through the route of particularization, in quest of a prime partition

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Abstract : This is a study on some ideas and structures, which intends to provide a proof of Goldbach's binary conjecture. The proof uses certain type of uniqueness (which may be called a self induced uniqueness), in a parametric case representing for the general one. Making a Hypothetically particular system and introducing a certain condition regarding it, various situations are analysed to confirm the existence of a Goldbach partition. Redefining or conceiving of some matters like 'list', 'choice', successivity and 'base' serves as circumstantial necessity to give the proper formats of the arguments.

Introduction

To prove that any even positive integer greater than or equal to 4, is a sum of two primes, the main focus is given on the analysis of circumstances regarding the even positive integers greater than 6. In this proof, there is conceived a parametric system, to represent for the similar general one there. Special status is attributed to this system, so that we can consider it as an arbitrarily particular one, especially due to certain attributions to the identities (the word 'identity' refers to 'the expressed individual concept of something') and arrangements of some of its characteristic elements. The proof follows the principle : if a system is completely expressed by only some particular things, the things being its components, constituting the conceptual expression of the system, just by appearing together, then each one of the things becomes unique in its respective role in that system (Note : The principle is universally true, because our whole consideration regarding this system is particular; besides, the identity of the particular thing, itself serves as a necessity for the unique identification associated to the thing, in question of fitting in its role there. For example, let some system is completely expressed by its particular components a, b and c, in the way as described above, then the component 'a' is unique for the role of being 'a' in that system, similar arguments hold for the components 'b' and 'c' too.) Aspects of a special column of steps is going to be discussed in the following course of the proof, where there can be felt a shadow of Vieta Jumping, but as the things proceed, we see a significant deviation from its usual procedure. To evade the circularity of reasoning appearing there, it becomes imperative to introduce a condition C_s , in relation to the particular system. Except for some widely used preliminary mathematical terms & concepts, ordinary english is as far as maintained throughout the body of arguments and discussions.

Please note : Every symbol 'p' with or without any suffix denotes some prime number. $a|b$ means a divides b and $a \nmid b$ means a doesn't divide b. n is a finite natural number. The word 'prime' will hereafter mean 'a prime number' and 'composite' refer to 'a natural number greater than 1,

that is not a prime '. The sign ' \exists ' means 'there exist'. Other signs denote meanings as per general convention.

The proposed proof of Goldbach's binary conjecture

First stage

Proposition : There is at least one prime p ($3 \leq p < n$) for every $2n > 6$ such that $p \nmid 2n$.

Proof : For any even $2n > 6$, at least one of the even integers $2n-2$ and $2n+2$ is not an integral power of 2. Now $n-1$ or $n+1$ is divisible by at least one prime p ($3 \leq p < n$).

So $p \mid 2(n-1) \Rightarrow p \nmid 2(n-1)+2 \Rightarrow p \nmid 2n$, or alternatively $p \mid 2(n+1) \Rightarrow p \nmid 2(n+1)-2 \Rightarrow p \nmid 2n$

Suitably using any of the above two alternative results we can prove the claim.

Second stage

Let $2n > 6$ (n being a particular natural number). Now consider a particular prime p_1 ($3 \leq p_1 < n$) such that $p_1 \nmid 2n$.

Let $2n-p_1$ is divisible by a prime p_2 , where $p_2 < n$. (For the case $p_2 > n$, see the 'Consequences' part later, in this proof of Goldbach's binary conjecture)

So there can be a column of similar steps :

$\exists p_2$, such that $p_2 \mid 2n-p_1$, where $p_2 < n$

$\exists p_3$, such that $p_3 \mid 2n-p_2$, where $p_3 < n$

...

...

$\exists p_k$, such that $p_k \mid 2n-p_{k-1}$, where $p_k < n$

(Since any $2n-p_{k-1}$ is smaller than $2n$, it is clear that until $2n-p_{k-1}$ remains composite, p_k is necessarily smaller than n and evidently odd.)

Where, in this case, the primes p_2, p_3, \dots (each being less than n) are taken in such a manner, as far as possible, that each one is different from all the other primes (i.e, 'p' elements, also including p_1 ; in case, n itself happens to be a prime there, it is excluded from this consideration, though it is clear that, every 'p' element is different from n) appearing previous to itself in the above steps.

[Clarification : $2n-p_1$ is odd and has no prime factor which can be equal to p_1 , otherwise $p_1 \mid 2n$.

Now the above manner of selections of prime factors works at least for p_2 (since, $p_2 \neq p_1$).

Therefore, we can reasonably presume that, there is always an arbitrary limit upto how far this manner of selections of primes works.]

It can easily be proved that no such prime divides $2n$ (since any $p_k \neq p_{k-1}$).

The operation of getting p_2, p_3, \dots must end at some p_k , otherwise there will be infinitely many different primes $< n$; k is a finite positive integer. We henceforth shall call p_1 as 'starting prime'. We further call the primes p_2, p_3, \dots, p_k (all being different, where p_k is 'one' last available of them; making provision for the possibility of having, more than one, eligible prime, to the purpose of finding one such last available, at least for sake of argument, from the same last step, so as not to lose any kind of generality; that is why 'one' is used instead of 'the' there; however this provision, intended for maintaining no loss of generality, is unlikely to disturb the the following reasonings) (continuing from back) as different outputs or simply as outputs. We refer to such column, consisting of those successively arranged steps, as shown before and contributing the said outputs, as the column of steps.

[Note : The number of 'p' primes appearing in such a column of steps can't be smaller than 2, since only one such prime, by itself, can't make any such column or step.

And take the example, where $n=14$; for a starting prime 3, there is, $3 \nmid 2 \times 14$; so we see the first step, ' $\exists 5$ such that, $5 \mid (2 \times 14 - 3)$, where $5 < 14$ '. Again, $2 \times 14 - 5$ isn't composite and

in this case there is, $3 < 5 < 14 < 23 < 2 \times 14$. Therefore the column of steps ends here (i.e, at the step giving out its own last output and of course, just at the very first step here), is comprised of only one step having just two ' p ' elements, i.e, the starting prime and the last output. Therefore $k=2$ in this case.

So we can conclude, for any such column $k \geq 2$.]

[Note : ' Order of a list or a column ' or ' order of the members/items of a list or a column ' means, ' certain arrangement of the members/items of the list or the column respectively, in succession ', and in this connection ' ordered ' means ' arranged in succession '.]

Hence we can put two important observations.

Observation (1) : For a particular p_1 we can choose arbitrarily particular p_2, p_3, \dots, p_k (p_k being the last available different output for the column of steps mentioned before, where p_1 is the starting prime) and in this way they (alongwith p_1) constitute a Unique Path : an ordered list (see definition of list in ' A discussion on list, choice, successivity & base ' later) of successive particular selections {Clarification : arbitrarily particular outputs are one time particular selection of primes, placed in a particular order, those which can be attributed to this list within the scopes available there; note, like the last step of the column, other steps too may possess the potential of giving more than one primes, as the outputs there; so we select a particular prime, available from a step, as the output of that step and assign the corresponding ordinality to it; besides, p_1 is already a hypothetically particular choice (though it's not an output available from any step) for the column and thereby it is fixed for the same column; further note, once the particular selections are made, their ordinalities get automatically and uniquely assigned there (see the structure of the column of steps); hence, the order of the ' p ' primes of the column there, becomes particular too, in respect to the primes themselves}, (continuing from back) from the prime factors of successive $2n-p_t$'s, p_t 's starting from p_1 , where p_1 is also included in the same list and put in the first place (i.e, before p_2).

Again, as the members of the Unique Path and their ordinalities (i.e, successive positions) there, are particular ones, the column of steps, from which the Unique Path derives, is also a particular one, i.e, each step has its own particular successive position in the column and has an individually particular character as well {Clarification : From the structural formation of the column we make the following deductions. Since, each p_t (except p_1) is available from $2n-p_{t-1}$, if p_t 's are particular, then $2n-p_{t-1}$'s have to be so (since n is particular too) and therefore, concerning successive positions of these $2n-p_{t-1}$'s in the column are particular too and they are compatible with the particular ordinalities of the corresponding outputs, available from the corresponding steps, which steps contain such $2n-p_{t-1}$'s as well, in appropriate places. Further, as p_1 is the initial particular choice, $2n-p_1$ becomes particular too. Finally we can say, the column of steps itself becomes a particular one, where every step of it, is also particular and has been assigned a particular successive position in the column.}. Obviously, the column of steps can be interpreted as a vertical list of steps too.

Important : There is a point worth notice that, as the Unique Path is particular in values and order of its member primes, so its generating column of steps is also particular and they are different from similar other Unique Paths and associated columns of steps respectively. Moreover, in our discussions, when we attach the word ' particular ' to some thing, we must presume that the ' particular ' thing is different from similar other things of its kind also.

Hypothetically particular system : From the above discussions and the hypothetical particularization described there, we can make an arbitrarily particular system that is completely expressed only by the aforesaid column of steps and the Unique Path generated from it, both of which are particular, where both of them constitute the conceptual expression of the system, being its components and just by appearing together (see, the discussion on such system in the Introduction). In various places in the ongoing discussions we will make reference of the system as Hypothetically particular system and symbolise it as ' S ' (often we will refer to this system as ' system S ' or simply as ' S ' there too). Every such system is particular and thereby different from similar other systems; therefore, a kind of uniqueness can be attributed to the system, in any situation, introducing a condition C_s there, regarding the system S. We define C_s as : if in a situation there exists a list, then the list must be one of the conceptual components of S (here, the ' conceptual components of S ', only refers to the column of steps and the Unique Path derived from it; they are categorised with such name to make a reference for the kind of role they are playing in construction of the system S; in later course of the proof, we will come to see, only two lists serve as the conceptual components of S; see the fourth paragraph in the ' Clarifications ', following ' Requirements regarding the value of p_{k+1} ' later). Further, observing the structure of the column of steps and the assigned ordinalities of the ' p ' elements there, we can say, the column of steps and the corresponding Unique Path are unique for each other, in any hypothetically particular system such as S (because, any change in the Unique Path or its associated column of steps, will destroy both the particularity and uniqueness of the system).

A situation refers to some particular consideration. Note, the definition of a Hypothetically particular system, describes the situation, in which the system is formed. There we get only two lists (we will come to see later, there are only two lists serving as the conceptual components of S; see the fourth paragraph in the ' Clarifications ', following ' Requirements regarding the value of p_{k+1} ' later). Therefore, we can say, there is at least one situation, which comply with the condition C_s .

For, the word ' particular ' in ' Hypothetically particular system ', might mislead to a sense of only some isolated case and not a general one representing for all such cases, we should convince ourselves of the fact that, it (i.e, the word) alludes to only a different angle of viewing the general case there, reckoning each individually special case (i.e, every such case that has the format of the general case but having particular constituents) of this general case as arbitrarily particular.

Observation (2) : p_k being the last different output in the said column of steps ($p_k < n$, where, p_k is available from $2n - p_{k-1}$, as a factor of it), proceeding similarly beyond it we get a prime p_{k+1} from $2n - p_k$, where $p_{k+1} | 2n - p_k$, with the exception that, in this case p_{k+1} not necessarily to be less than n (we will proceed with this ' not necessarily ' status, as the step here is somewhere different in character from the earlier steps). Besides, as this step goes past that of the last different output, the stipulation for outputs to be different from the previously appeared ' p ' primes in the Unique Path, vanishes automatically for p_{k+1} .

Further note, in a situation, having the existence of the system S and complying with the condition C_s , there can exist the prime p_{k+1} too. But, p_{k+1} doesn't make any list with any element of the system there in that situation. p_{k+1} is not any part of the system S and the ordinality $k+1$ is attributed to it, only to the purpose of isolating it from the ' p ' elements (i.e, members) of the Unique Path.

Now if, $p_{k+1} < n$, the supposition there implies p_{k+1} is a recycled prime, i.e, the value of p_{k+1} is one of $p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots, p_k$ (since p_k is the last available different output for that said column of

k-1 unique steps, p_1 being the starting prime). **(We will resume the proof again after discussing some topics below.)**

A discussion on list, choice, successivity & base

We define 'a list', as a mathematical expression constructed by successive (i.e, arranged by putting one item after the another) mentioning of items, such that no two items should be identical (i.e, same) there; and define 'a choice', as a selection (not only from a list) of mentioned item/s (for the definition of a choice this much perception is enough, as we need defining the pure form of a choice here; in usual practice, we see a choice ' from this ' or 'for that ' and similar other conditional elements associated to it, but these are other questions, where the purposes involved there exceed ' a selection of mentioned items ', the only purpose described in the definition of a choice). When a choice is associated with ' for this ' or ' from that ' type of conditional elements, it may be different for different cases, though the selected items in such different cases may be same. [Note : Interestingly, selecting a mentioned item \Rightarrow selecting the item, again, selecting an item \Rightarrow the item getting already mentioned there (intuitively, we can't choose or select any item without the item being mentioned somewhere). Therefore, we can say, ' selecting an item ' and 'selecting a mentioned item ' are same for the purpose of the selection of the item and the later is just a detailed form of the former. Hence, the definition of choice is given as a detailed and comprehensive form of that operation.]

Apart from defining ' list ' and ' choice ', it requires here to introduce two new ideas, namely, ' successivity of a list ' and ' base of a list '.

Successivity of a list : Successivity of a list or just a successivity, is a property of coming one item after another in some certain sequence, such that no two items are identical there, subject to a necessity that the list so formed, has at least two items; the property itself is considered as a mathematical entity, that is unique for the list formed as per the successivity in question there (provided the list has at least two items), considering the identities and order of the items of the list. The definition of a successivity can be clarified by stating : a list has a certain successivity \Leftrightarrow the list has a certain order for its items, provided the list has at least two items. Moreover, successivity and order of a list (having at least two items) are unique for each other. Once there is a change in order, there is corresponding change in successivity, where the number and individual identities of the items in a list doesn't change, and conversely. Further, when there is a change in number or individual identities, of the items in a list, there is a change in successivity too, though the converse is not always true.

Base of a list: We define a base of a list or simply a base, as a mathematical entity, constructed by mentioning of all items of a list, so that just the appearances of the items there, by themselves, can make such construction, where such a mentioning must be without any kind of successivity pertaining to those items there. A base is an imaginary entity, which is endowed with no successivity at all regarding its items there. When we attribute certain successivity to a base having at least two items, the base becomes a list. Like a list, no two items of a base are identical. [A base has some properties those are similar to a set. Like a set it can have a sub-base and a superbase, proper or improper whatever. The definitions for these concepts can be easily made following the definitions of the similar concepts regarding a set, those are defined in connection to a

set in set theory. But a base differs in some ways from a set too. For example, sometimes a set can have no element at all (i.e, void set), but no mentioning of item implies no base. Therefore a base is always non empty (i.e, at least one item is mentioned there) unlike a void set.]

If a base is constituted of the items, those are not mentioned in any list anywhere, then the base isn't the base of any list and thereby contradicts the definition of a base of a list. Therefore existence of a base always imply the existence of some list, that is constituted of just all the items of that base somewhere. To be specific, if a base has existence in a certain situation, then some list consisting of just all items of the base, must have existence in the same situation, and conversely. On the other hand, if a list has no existence in a certain situation, then its base has no existence in that situation, and conversely.

An important question on the existence of a successivity may arise here, regarding the discussion over an issue : if a list contains only one item, then its base also has exactly the same mentioning, and thereby only and same item, as the list itself; is the definition of a base complied with in this case? We should be assured that, there has occurred no kind of illegitimacy in this case, since the existence of a successivity of any kind, needs the existence of at least two items there in the concerned list, which is not the case described here.

(We may often term the items constructing a list or a base as its ' members ' in different circumstances occurring in various places in the proof of Goldbach's binary conjecture and related other discussions.)

Now we may think, whether omitting every item or member of a list, except the intended one for the choice, is necessary for a choice of only one item from that list (provided the list contains more than one item as its members). For, if that isn't necessary, there can be any other way for such choice, where more than one item of the list can be saved from any possible omission involved in that way. Hence, to prove the absurdity of the above option it suffices to prove that :

we choose only one item from a certain list \Leftrightarrow we omit the rest of the items from the list (provided the list contains more than one item as its members) •••{lemma (a)}

Proof : Suppose the list has at least two members.

First, we answer the question as to why an omission from a list is necessary, in the question of choosing a certain item from the list, where the list has at least two members.

To choose a certain item from a list that has at least two members, we have to discard off the members of the list, from our consideration for the requirement described in the l.h.s of the lemma statement, which members don't stand for the right candidate for such selection; in other words, we have to exclude those members, which are not our intended one, from our considered role for a right candidate there; otherwise there will be more than one right candidate for such a choice. Here we are given a list in our consideration to work on, to the purpose of choosing such a right candidate from it. When we select a certain item from a list, in our consideration for the role of a right candidate to that end, fits the very item only. Since, we require to exclude the unfit ones, from our consideration for such a role of a right candidate, as shown above, and the same consideration pertains the given list as well, therefore, in this case, the said 'discarding off ' or ' exclusion ' from the consideration for the role of a right candidate, must be interpreted as omission/s from the given list. Hence, we see some omission/s from the given list, is necessary for the requirement described in the l.h.s of the lemma statement.

Next, suppose the r.h.s of the lemma is not always necessary for the proposed choice in the lemma, even when some omission/s are involved in the process of choosing.

A list is an expression of mentioned items and we have to choose only one item from the list, in other words, we have to select only one mentioned item from the list.

Now, if we preserve at least one more member of this list, while preserving the item intended for the proposed choice described in the l.h.s of the lemma, from some omission which the above choice necessitates, such that we preserve that extra item of the list alongwith the above intended item itself also, thereby including both of them in the set of selected items, for the choice in question described in the lemma (this is the first kind of omission we may discuss of, w.r.t selecting a certain member of the list),

then there will be at least two mentioned items of the list for such a choice, where none of them can be excluded from the consideration for a right candidate for the proposed choice in the lemma.

Therefore, to satisfy the proposed requirement meant in the l.h.s of the above lemma statement, in this case (i.e, where at least one more item of the list, alongwith the intended one for the choice described in the l.h.s of the lemma, is saved from the omission there), we have no other option than to accept at least two members of the given list simultaneously, as selected items for the proposed choice there,

which is absurd in view of the hypothesis that, we choose only one item from the list {since we have to choose (i.e, select the mentioned item from the list, as obvious here) only one item as per our requirement described there}.

Hence, the omission of the aforesaid first kind, regarding preservation of at least one extra item in the list alongwith the intended one, to the purpose of the proposed choice described in the lemma statement, becomes incompetent to serve for the purpose of choosing only one item from the list.

[Clarifications : While studying the establishment of the absurdity above, the reader may ask that : though more than one item of the list are assumed to have been saved from the omission executed there, can we, just by virtue of such preservation, consider these items as selected ones (for sake of argument) to meet the requirement for the choice described in the l.h.s of the lemma? This question arises more because, such selection of more than one member of the list, doesn't match our requirement stated in the l.h.s of the lemma statement; besides, nothing has been said on such selection of more than one member, in the lemma statement. Now, in that imaginary case (i.e, where at least one more item of the list, alongwith the intended one for the choice described in the l.h.s of the lemma, is saved from the omission there), it is obvious that we have no other option than to accept the said absurd selection set, to the purpose of choosing only one item from the list, if we can't discard off every member of the list, other than the intended one for the choice described in the l.h.s of the lemma statement, from our consideration for the right candidate for such a choice; since our inability to exclude some item of the list, from our consideration of a right candidate to the purpose of choosing a certain item from the list, automatically selects that inexcludable item for the role of that right candidate there, therefore, in such imaginary case, for sake of argument, we have to accept more than one member of the list as the selected items meeting our purpose of choosing only one item there.]

Again, as per the l.h.s of the above lemma statement, we can certainly select the intended only one item (at least hypothetically, i.e, we have already assumed such choice is possible there), which implies it can never be omitted from the list mentioned there (and thereby also implies the absurdity of omission of every item of the list, including omission of the intended one, in question of the choice of that item there). This

is the second kind of omission, we may discuss of, in relation to the proposed choice in the lemma.

Further, we discuss the possibility of the omission of a third kind, in question of choosing a certain item from the list : the omission of all mentioned items, except the one intended to the purpose of such choice, from the list. As a result of such omission, the spared item gets automatically selected there (since, the possibility of a chosen item from the list is already hypothetically conceived in the lemma statement). Clearly, omission of this kind is sufficient to meet the requirement of the choice described in the l.h.s of the lemma (since, the leftover of the list, resulting in from the omission of this third kind, is the only compatible one with the requirement described in the l.h.s of the lemma). Hence we conclude, the residue of the list (evidently, the item in question), obtained by this omission, serves for the evidence of the sufficient condition described in the lemma.

[Comment : The three kinds of omission described before are mutually exclusive (i.e, if one takes place others cannot), in question of the proposed choice described in the lemma and together they become exhaustive in this question (i.e, together they cover up all kinds of omission, those can be discussed in the same question as above).]

Hence, examining every possible state of the mentioned items in the list, regarding the effects of omissions on that list, in question of choosing only one item (i.e, a certain mentioned item) from it, we can say, the omission of every items of the list, except the one intended to the purpose of choosing a certain item from the list, is necessary and sufficient, for the proposed choice described in the l.h.s of the lemma.

Therefore our claim in the above lemma is true.

In all situations this lemma works equally, no matter, if a list (having at least two members) is formed independently or its formation depends on some necessary condition, and this idea is very important in the following course of the proof of Goldbach's binary conjecture.

Resuming the proof again :...

(A declaration : In the following discussions ' recycled value ' will mean one of p_1, p_2, \dots, p_k , that is intended for the purpose of choosing a value for p_{k+1} , ' recycling purpose ' will mean ' the purpose of choosing such a value for p_{k+1} ' and ' recycled choice ' will mean 'the choice of such a value for p_{k+1} '.)

An Important note : Since S is particular, C_s is also particular on account of its affiliation with the particular system S , when C_s is seen among other conditions similar to it, those could be made, in respect with other systems similar to S , following the same format as used for the condition C_s itself. For our convenience, we will examine, uphold, decline or provisionally assume the authenticity of the matters, pertaining to the elements and features of S , in the following discussions, in respect to the supposition that the concerning situations comply with the condition C_s ; these studies together represent for the similar studies, regarding the general case dealing with every $2n > 6$, on the question of validity of Goldbach's binary conjecture there. [For definition of C_s see the paragraph titled 'Hypothetically particular system ' before]

Now, we will prove that, if a recycled value can be chosen as p_{k+1} , in compliance with the condition C_s , then it should be necessarily and sufficiently chosen in the way of choosing it from the Unique Path described in Observation (1), where the said way of choosing, is the only way for choosing a recycled value in compliance with the condition C_s .

Requirements regarding the value of p_{k+1} : Let p_{k+1} is a recycled prime. Clearly the value of p_{k+1} has to be chosen from the base alone, consisting of the same and just all primes, those which the Unique Path consists of, in a situation complying with the condition C_s [case (1)] {we will see later, in a situation complying with the condition C_s , there is no existence of any proper sub-base or proper superbase of that proposed base described in the case (1), in the Clarifications below}; otherwise p_{k+1} will not be a recycled prime, because, if p_{k+1} takes a recycled value, then the choice of a 'p' prime, to the purpose of finding a value for p_{k+1} , has to be considered from the mentioned items of Unique Path, irrespective of any particular order of those items, to maintain no loss of generality until this point. Again, as per definition of the base of a list, there is no successivity for the members of a base, which implies more than one list, of different particular orders for their respective members (where number of the members is ≥ 2), can be made with just all members of the same base, attributing successivities of different kinds to it; ... (We will continue this paragraph later again after some other discussions and proofs of two more lemmas)

[Clarifications : In the above paragraph it has been stated that we have to choose the value for p_{k+1} , from the base of the Unique Path alone. So, why is that necessary? The precondition for the choice of a recycled value is that, it must not be anything other than one of the members mentioned in the Unique Path. Then it has to be one of them (though not everyone has a chance, especially p_k can never be chosen as a recycled value; but there is no harm in taking it in the association of the 'p' primes of the Unique Path, to meet this precondition there, since there are always more than one member in the Unique Path). Now, if we want to choose one of them, then we must select it from the mentioned prime members of the Unique Path, provided the choice should be done irrespective of any certain successivity at that point, so as not to lose any kind of generality there (see the above paragraph titled ' Requirements regarding the value of p_{k+1} '). Now, the base of the Unique Path has existence, in a situation complying with the condition C_s . Therefore by definition of a base, we have to choose the intended prime from the base consisting of the same and just all primes, those which the Unique Path consists of, in that situation. Further, we have to choose the recycled value from the above base alone, as in the later paragraphs we will come to see, there is no existence of a proper sub-base or a proper superbase of the aforesaid base, in a situation complying with the condition C_s .

On the question whether the recycled value could be selected from a proper superbase of the base of the Unique Path, we can say, such a superbase can be constructed by adding more item/s, those are different from the primes of the base of the Unique Path, to the base of the Unique Path itself, subject to a condition that, the said superbase has its existence in a situation, that complies with the condition C_s .

Since a base is actually ' a base of some list ', therefore to meet the condition for the existence of the above superbase, a list having this proper superbase as its own base, requires to have its own existence in a situation, that complies with C_s too.

In the Observation (1) we have already noticed that the column of steps is also a vartical list of steps. Therefore, only two particular lists (i.e, the column of steps and the Unique path) completely express the system S, being the components of S, those constitute the conceptual expression of S, just by appearing together. (These two certain lists completely express the individual identities of the conceptual components of the system S; thereby we can say, these two particular lists, appropriately fit in roles of the conceptual components of S, without any objection.)

Intuitively, for sake of argument, to make a proper superbase as said before, we consider here three kinds of entities, which by addition to the base of the Unique Path,

might make a proper superbase of it : the system S itself, any of the conceptual components of S and lastly any entity other than the former two; such considerations propose three different kinds of proper superbases according to certain kinds of additions there.

We know that, the system S doesn't allow any entity, in the role of any of its conceptual components, other than the one already specified to that purpose; thereby we conclude the aforesaid conceptual components of the system S are unique for it, in question of fitting in the roles of above kind (by the principle of uniqueness regarding the components of a particular system, discussed in the ' Introduction ' part before). Therefore, any list, that has a proper superbase of the base of the Unique Path, as its own base, which is constructed in the way of any addition, to the base of the Unique Path, as described in the above paragraph, cannot be identical to any of the aforesaid lists expressing the individual identities of the conceptual components of S, and thereby can't be identical to any of the said conceptual components.

Now, in a situation complying with the condition C_s , if we imagine the existence of a list, where the list is different from the above two particular lists fitting in the roles of the conceptual components of S, then the idea directly contradicts the condition C_s .

{Comments on the consistency of C_s in a situation : Apart from addressing the question regarding the existence of a list, whose base can be formed by adding more item/s, to the members of the base of the Unique Path, the above argument deals similarly with the existence of a list, whose base can be formed by removing some members from the base of the Unique Path too.

Now, the question is, as every member of the Unique Path or the column of steps has its individual existence in the system S, whether there could be any self-contradiction for C_s , in a situation.

We know any member of the Unique Path or any step of the column has its individual existence in the system. So there may be an idea that, some member/s of the Unique Path or the column of steps, those don't cover up every member of the Unique Path or the column of steps respectively, could make some list too, in some situation, where the one of the conceptual components of S, from which such member/s may come, is existent. Certainly, such member/s of the Unique Path/column of steps can make a list, but not in every situation; the definition of a list gives the description of the construction of it, but it doesn't imply any item/s of it can make a list, irrespective to any given condition or setup regarding them; in fact, a list becomes valid, only if it's constructed, in agreement with the conditions pertaining its existence. If in a situation complying with the condition C_s , there exists a list, the list must be one of the conceptual components of the system S. But, compliance with the condition C_s in a situation, doesn't necessarily assert the existence of any of the conceptual components of the system S, in that situation (from the definition of C_s , it is clear that, where nothing about the existence of a list is said in the description of a situation, C_s itself alone gives no certainty on the existence of any list in that situation at all); nor the condition C_s approves any list, formed with a number of members of the Unique Path or the column of steps, that is not one of the conceptual components of the system S; moreover, C_s doesn't approve that list even by force of the existence of some of the conceptual components from which the said members come, in that situation, though C_s approves (but not asserts) the existence of any of the conceptual components, in appropriate circumstances, in a situation complying with C_s . Besides, we conclude the individual existences of element/s, or their possible arrangement in succession, leads to no self-contradiction for condition C_s too.}

Now, it is clear that, no list having any of the three kinds of proper superbases proposed earlier, as its own base, can exist, if the construction of the list has to comply with the condition C_s .

Hence, covering all the aspects concerning every type of entity which could be examined, in question of making a proper superbase of the base of the Unique Path, we can say, to comply with the condition C_s , the base of the Unique Path doesn't allow any proper superbase at all.

On the question of choosing the recycled prime, from a proper sub-base of the base of the Unique path, we can say, that is not possible, if the job has to be done in compliance with the condition C_s . A proper sub-base of the base of the Unique Path, can be formed by omitting some items (necessarily, not all of them) of the original base, if that sub-base exists in a situation, that complies with the condition C_s . Studying the reasonings regarding the possibility of making a proper superbase of the base of the Unique Path, as shown before, we can find the arguments, as to why no such list, that takes any proper sub-base of the base of the Unique Path, as its own base, can exist in a situation, that complies with the condition C_s , and thereby we can show the proper sub-base in question too becomes inexistent there.]

(Note : When we discuss anywhere in this proof, about a list formed from/formed with the members of/consisting of the members of a base etc, we should keep in mind that there is no member in that list, which is not a member of the same base. Similar proposition also holds, if we interchange the words ' base ' and ' list ' in the former one.)

We will now prove two important lemmas. These lemmas could have been included in ' A discussion on list, choice, successivity & base ', but considering their relevance in our current discussion, they are put here.

Lemma (b) : We can choose an item from a base \Rightarrow we can choose it from a list, that can be formed with the members (not necessarily all) of the same base, where one of them is the item in question, provided that the list exists (obviously, in the situation where the base exists)

Proof : If we can choose an item from a base, then the item is a member of the base.

So the list described in the above proposition of lemma (b), can be formed from the said base there \Rightarrow the item in question is mentioned somewhere in the list (if the list exists in the situation where the base exists) and therefore we can undoubtedly choose it from that list. {As we have already admitted that, we select it from the base, therefore, it already gets selected and the said item is mentioned in the list too; therefore the result follows; alternatively, we can omit every member of the list, other than the item in question, the result will be the same, see lemma (a).}

This proves the lemma (b).

Now the another lemma.

Lemma (c) : If some certain item x can be chosen from a base B , then the operation of choosing it from the base B , can only be performed in the way of choosing it from the list, that can be formed with the members of B (not necessarily the list should be consisting of all members of B), x being one of those members, provided the list has existence in the situation where the base B exists.

Proof : Since B is always non empty,

we choose an arbitrary member of B and examine if it is x . If yes, we end the operation of choosing there (Note : a single item too can make a list). If it is not x , we have to put it (say x_1) aside and choose another item from the sub-base B_1 of the base B , where B_1 contains every member of B , except the item chosen first and put aside; examine the second item as before and so on. The successive operations continue until we get x .

Now, in the process described above we get a list, x_1, x_2, \dots, x , from which evidently we get x . (Where the list exists)

This proves the lemma (c), where x not necessarily to be chosen from a list consisting of every member of B , provided the list has existence in the situation where the base exists. (For detailed arguments on this proof see the Explanations below.) For the complementary proof establishing a general case, see later.

[Explanations : The way, how x can be chosen from B , as shown in the above proof, can be formulated as, 'choose x (to the purpose of choosing only x) from B and put aside the other members of it those are not x ' (note, this conceptual structure is compatible with the concepts of matters, regarding the idea of the proposed choice in the lemma; every conceptual element in this formula, exists somewhere among those concepts of matters, in the lemma, or can be logically deduced from them). Now obviously x alone can be chosen in the above manner. This serves for the sufficient condition for choosing a certain x from B .

Next, suppose x can be chosen from B , in a way, that provides no room for the above manner. Then the other way implies, at least one member of B , other than the member x (supposing B has more than one member), cannot be put aside (i.e, can't be excluded from the consideration for the role of a right candidate, in question of the proposed selection) and thereby gets selected in question of the proposed selection, alongwith x itself (the only possible consequence regarding the cardinality of selected items in such a way; a selection set or bag may also be conceived here for convenience), and hence that selected other member can be made a companion of x in the bag of selection in question, which is absurd on the ground of selecting only x from B , for any B having more than one member.

Again, for sake of argument, if we imagine a way, for choosing only x from B , that provides a room the aforesaid formulated manner, provided that, the imagined way itself, is not the said formulated manner, then there remains some matter or part, as the element of construction, of the concept, of that imagined way, where the said matter or part provides no room for the factor that, choosing x from B to be done in the aforesaid formulated manner (there must be such a matter or part as said above, in the structure of the imagined way; we roughly may call that matter or part, as a surplus matter; the reason for conceiving the existence of such a surplus matter is, that the above imagined way provides a room for the said formulated manner, where the imagined way itself isn't identical to the said formulated manner). Clearly, the surplus matter has nothing to do with the choosing of only x from B ; otherwise, it will be the aforesaid different way for 'choosing only x from B ', discussed in the above paragraph. Therefore, getting rid of that useless involvement, of such surplus matter there, we can say, only one way, for choosing x from B , is involved in that case and that is the said formulated manner itself.

Further, though the idea of putting the items aside, those are not x , has come in the discussion, such items are not any part of the selection in question, despite being mentioned in this course (since the choice described in the aforesaid formula, can be performed only to fulfill a certain requirement, therefore the members of B , those may be put aside, cannot be reckoned as selected to the purpose of choosing only x from B). For B having only x , the aforesaid formulated way is obviously the only way of selecting it. Therefore we can take the way described by the formula 'choose x (to the purpose of choosing only x) from $B \dots$ that are not x ' as serving for the necessary condition and itself is the unique way for the selection of only x from B .

Now, in the process of choosing x from B , as described in the proof, we get a list x_1, x_2, \dots, x (since the operations have to be successive there) and the way formulated at the beginning of this Explanations, necessitates the provision for this list to the purpose of an execution in the said formulated manner (if the list exists in the situation where the

base exists). Therefore, the operations performed in compliance with that formulated manner, necessitates that there must be an option of choosing x from the above list, in this case (from now on, for our convenience, we suppose the list exists in the situation, where the base B exists, till the end of this Explanations), if such choice from the list is possible at all, as the option also serves to the purpose of the selection of x from B there. We confirm the possibility of such choice from the list, by force of the lemma (b). (Note, regarding the current proof of the lemma, we already have provisionally considered that, x can be chosen from B)

Next, if we imagine a situation, where x is chosen from B , as : x is chosen in the aforesaid formulated manner, but, x is not chosen from any list at all,

as we see, the aforesaid formulated manner of ' choosing only x from B ' does imply the provision for the aforesaid list (we have already supposed that the list exists) and thereby asserts that ' x is chosen from that list ', even in that imaginary situation, then we arrive at a contradiction there, which renders such situation absurd.

Finally, we resolve our doubt on, whether x is chosen from a list, formed with the members of B (not necessarily all), x itself being a member of the list, where the list is not the aforesaid list x_1, x_2, \dots, x or the extended/complete form of it (for such extended/complete form of the list, see, the paragraph below, regarding the completion of the proof of lemma (c), following the end of this Explanations),

by understanding that, the aforesaid list x_1, x_2, \dots, x or its extended/complete form, is just a general form of the list, derived by the application of the aforesaid formulated way, to which form the above proposed alternative list conforms.

Now, from the above discussions we can say, for the choice of only x from B , in the aforesaid formulated way, the necessary condition is,

x can be chosen from B , in the way of choosing it from the list x_1, x_2, \dots, x or its extended/complete form, where the concerned list exists (see the paragraph regarding the completion of the proof of lemma (c)). This necessary condition also serves for a way of ' choosing only x from B ', where the concerned list exists.

Now, the conceptual structure of the way, for ' choosing only x from B ', that is described by the above necessary condition, has no such part, that is not necessary for choosing only x from B .

Therefore, disregarding the involvement of the aforesaid formulated manner, we conclude (for, the reason, as to why we disregard the involvement of that formulated manner here, see Note below), the operation of ' choosing only x from B ', can be performed only in the way of choosing it from the list x_1, x_2, \dots, x or its extended/complete form, where the concerned list exists.]

Now for completion of the proof, so as to show the lemma holds for a general case, we proceed as : If in the partial proof earlier, we get x before finishing with all the members of B , then we can continue collecting items, to the purpose of putting them aside, from the rest of the members of B , those have not yet been selected/put aside, reckoning the items collected, in question of such collection, as not x , and put those collected items, in succession after x , so that we can make an extended/complete form of the list x_1, x_2, \dots, x , covering up to all members of B in this way, from which x can be chosen, if the list exists in the situation where B exists. Moreover, if in some situation, only the complete form of the list x_1, x_2, \dots, x , has existence, then the task of, 'choosing of only x from B ', can only be done in the way of choosing it from the above complete form of the list and therefore, the said task can be done, only in the way of choosing it from a list, formed with necessarily all members of B , in that situation. (Reasonings are similar to those stated in the above Explanations part, we just need suitably adjust them to serve for this case; for, any confusion regarding ' only in the way of choosing it ', see Note below.).

[Note : x can be chosen from B , only in a manner of choosing it, that is described by the formula 'choose x (to the purpose of choosing only x) from $B \dots$ that are not x ', in the Explanations part before; and further, for the choice of x from B in the said formulated manner, there the necessary condition is, the choice of only x from B , to be done in the way of choosing x from the aforesaid list {we consider here the general form of such list, covering every member of the B or not, whatever, as it fits to the purpose of choosing x from B , in the concerning situation (see, Explanations); the need for the existence of the list being satisfied; in fact, if every list, formed with whatever members of B , has no existence in some situation, then the base B itself has no existence there too}. Moreover, we can make the list independently, without any help of the aforesaid formulated manner too, where the list exists. Therefore, from the viewpoint of logic, both of the ways regarding 'choosing only x from B ', as said above, are same in essence and character, however different they may look.]

Hence, the general case for the lemma (c) is proven.

Now the above lemmas lead to a more specific option for choosing the recycled value, that is to say, (continuing back from the earlier unfinished paragraph titled, 'Requirements regarding the value of p_{k+1} '), ... so therefrom, discarding every other possibility {an auxiliary case (3) in this connection will be discussed later}, we can say, the recycled value can be chosen from the Unique Path only (as a method for the choice of the recycled value), when the choice has to be from the base alone, consisting of just all prime members of the said Unique Path, when the choice should be made in compliance with the condition C_s . We refer to this case as, case (2).

[Note that, the case (1) and case (2) here, though look different, are not mutually exclusive at all. Moreover, from the lemma (c) it is clear that, choosing the recycled value from the base consisting of just all primes the Unique Path consists of \Leftrightarrow choosing the recycled value from the Unique Path also.]

Proof : Take the case (1).

Choosing a prime as p_{k+1} from the base consisting of just all prime members of the Unique Path, implies, choosing it from at least one list that can be formed with the same and just all primes of this base, where the list has its existence in a situation, that complies with C_s . {From the lemma (c), and from the fact that, any proper sub-base or proper superbase of the base of the Unique Path is inexistent, in a situation complying with the condition C_s , thereby asserting the concerning lists, which take these proper sub-bases or superbases as their own bases, to be also inexistent there; see Clarifications under the unfinished paragraph titled 'Requirements regarding the value of p_{k+1} '.}

Let the recycled value is taken in a way, as from such a list, that is formed with just all prime members of the base of the Unique Path, where the list has a successivity, different from that of the Unique Path. [Case (3)] Say the above list, that is different from the Unique Path, as the list L . (As the successivities of L and the Unique Path are different, these lists are different from each other too. See 'Successivity of a list' in 'A discussion on list, choice, successivity & base' before.)

Therefore, the case (1) described before puts forth only two sub cases {i.e, the cases (2) & (3)} for review here, where these sub cases together cover every kind of options to be examined, to the purpose of choosing the recycled value for p_{k+1} , from a list formed with just all members of the base of the Unique Path, in a situation complying with the condition C_s .

Since, to comply with the condition C_s , a list having just all prime members of the Unique Path, as all of its members, must be identical with the Unique Path itself,

the list L becomes inexistent in a situation that complies with C_s , thereby implying the incompatibility of the case (3), to the purpose of choosing a recycled value,

where the case (3) is considered for a review, in question of serving for an option, to the purpose of choosing a recycled value in compliance with the condition C_s .

Suppose a member p_r of the Unique Path is chosen as p_{k+1} . Therefore, the Unique Path contributes p_r . We can call it a sufficient condition for such choice in respect to the Case (1). (Because, the existence of the Unique Path in a situation complying with C_s , is approved by the condition C_s .)

Since, to comply with the condition C_s , the recycled value must be chosen from the base of the Unique Path alone and in that situation, the choice of the said recycled value must be performed in the way of choosing it from a list, having a base that is same as the base of the Unique Path, and further as we have already seen, that there can exist no such list other than the Unique Path, in a situation complying with the condition C_s ,

weighing every aspect of the aforesaid sub cases we can say, there remains no option for any list other than the above Unique Path, to choose the aforesaid recycled value from, to comply with the condition C_s . This gives the necessary condition in respect to the Case (1). Moreover, the case (2) provides the unique way for choosing of the aforesaid recycled value, when the choice has to be made in compliance with the condition C_s .

Now we will examine the reasonability of the consideration that, p_{k+1} is a recycled prime, in view of the condition C_s .

Since p_{k+1} is a singularly valued prime (i.e, only one value can be attributed to it from arbitrary options, at a time), a recycled value taken as p_{k+1} is also a singularly selected entity (i.e, only one prime that can be arbitrarily opted for that purpose, from the members of the Unique Path, at a time), in other words, we have to choose only one prime from the Unique Path, for the recycling purpose said before, at a time.

(The phrase ' at a time ' has been maintained in the arguments above, because, to maintain no loss of generality, we suppose p_{k+1} may take different values from different arbitrary options, i.e, more than one prime may divide $2n-p_k$; we have to deal with only one such option here.)

Now, for an arbitrarily particular p_1 , we obtain a Unique Path which must contain, at least a unique starting prime and a unique last output, i.e, the first and the last members of the Unique Path, which are unique for the Unique Path itself, where the members must be different from each other. (Since only one ' p ' element of the Unique Path, alone, can't make any step or column.)

Further, it has been already established that, to comply with the condition C_s , the choice of a prime from the base of the Unique Path, as the value of p_{k+1} , can be made only in the way of choosing it from the Unique Path.

Now, if the omission of any member or some members (necessarily not everyone) from the Unique Path, is considered valid in a situation complying with the condition C_s , then it will establish the existence of a list, which is a residual part of the Unique Path (i.e, residue of the Unique Path as a result of an omission executed on it), and which is formed with the members (necessarily not all) of the base of the Unique Path and thereby becoming different from the Unique Path, in the situation, having the existence of the Unique Path and complying with C_s there.

But the list, that can be obtained as a residual part of the Unique Path, as described in the above paragraph, has no existence in compliance with the condition C_s .

Hence, we arrive at a contradiction there.

(Though, the existence of the Unique Path is approved the condition C_s , the list, that is a residual part of the Unique Path, as said above, has no existence, in a situation

complying with the same condition and there is no self-contradiction for the condition C_s , in approving the existence of the Unique Path there, while declining the existence of the above residual part of the Unique Path; see, ' Comments on the consistency of C_s in a situation ', in the ' Clarifications ', following the earlier unfinished paragraph titled ' Requirements regarding the value of p_{k+1} '.)

Therefore we conclude, omission of a member or some of the members (necessarily not all) from the Unique Path is impossible, in a situation complying with the condition C_s .

It has been already shown that, for any Unique Path, $k \geq 2$. Therefore, from the above conclusion, it is clear that, in every possibility, in a situation, having the existence of the Unique Path and complying with the condition C_s , there remain at least two prime members, i.e, at least the starting prime and the last output, of the Unique Path, to be selected in question of choosing a prime from the members of the Unique Path, as a value of p_{k+1} , where none of members of the Unique Path is omissible.

So, we can say, that we can't omit, 'all primes other than that intended one for recycling purpose', from the Unique Path, in a situation, having the existence of the Unique Path and complying with the condition C_s ,

and as the recycled choice in question, from the Unique Path, requires at least one of the primes p_1 or p_k to be removed from it, besides all other required omissions, {see lemma (a)}

and farther as, the recycled value in question can be chosen, only in the way of choosing it from that Unique Path, in a situation, having the existence of the Unique Path and complying with the condition C_s , {from case (2)}

all these imply, we can't choose only one recycled value and therefore, can choose none of p_1, p_2, \dots, p_k , at all, in fact, as a value of p_{k+1} from that Unique Path there.

Consequences : Summing up all the discussions regarding the proposed choice of a recycled value for p_{k+1} ,

we conclude that p_{k+1} can't be a recycled prime, that implies p_{k+1} isn't less than n , and since $p_k < n$,

we are bound to accept the conclusion that, $p_{k+1} > n \Rightarrow p_{k+1} = 2n - p_k$.
 $[2n - p_k$ can't have a factor that is greater than n and smaller than itself, and $p_{k+1} \neq n$ for obvious reasons.]

Therefore, $2n = p_k + p_{k+1}$

We see, for every particular $2n > 6$, there can be construed some particular system like S , where $p_2 < n$, and certainly there can be conceived the situations as before, those comply with some condition formatted like C_s , w.r.t the particular system there, as conceived in the discussions before {because, there can be at least one situation, which complies with C_s and holds the existence of p_{k+1} ; from Observation (1) & (2)}. Further, we know that, if there is existence of some Goldbach partition for a particular $2n$, the very existence doesn't depend on the condition C_s . Hence, getting rid of the discussion regarding the condition C_s , we conclude, where $p_2 < n$, $2n = p_k + p_{k+1}$.

Take a look back at the beginning of the Second stage •••

Contrary to what we have assumed at there, if p_2 isn't less than n , then as $p_1 < n$, p_2 becomes greater than n . This implies $2n = p_1 + p_2$

[Reasons are similar as before]

Now, it is proven that for every particular $2n > 6$, the existence of a Goldbach partition is a reality. Considering this particular case to represent for the general one, we conclude, the conjecture holds for any $2n > 6$.

Finally, on the question whether the integers 6 & 4 comply the conjecture, we write $6 = 3 + 3$ and $4 = 2 + 2$.

Therefore, Goldbach's binary conjecture holds for every $2n \geq 4$.

Epilogue : From the foregoing discussions, we can hope to get a complete and airtight proof of Goldbach's binary conjecture, as every arbitrarily particular case is only a different angle to view the general one, as said before. The system S and condition C_s , get always possible in appropriate circumstances, as per our rational discretion, though there may be thoughts about what should happen, if the situations turn different from the aforesaid hypothetical ones complying with the condition C_s . For instance, if some situation holds the existence of a list, that is not identical to any of the Unique Path or associated column of steps, what may be the fate of a recycled prime, or whether any other kind of system could show the existence of a Goldbach partition etc. But that is an other story and we don't have any need to discuss on them for our purpose as of now.

References

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